

Standard Operating Procedure

Title: Sample preparation for the determination of microplastics in milk powder by use of citric acid and higher temperature

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1. Scope and application

Detection of microplastics (1-1000 µm) in milk is challenging. The mass of microplastics expected is very low. The matrix is complex due to proteins in the milk, which are not soluble in water and contaminate the GC/MS systems during detection. This standard operating procedure (SOP) is developed to remove the proteins from milk powder before detection as easy, fast and cheap sample preparation method. Matrix reduction is done with citric acid. The samples are baby milk powder as food for newborns. This SOP is specifically designed for protein reduction in the milk matrix to produce samples, which can be measured in TED-GC/MS (Thermal Extraction Desorption – Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry) to determine the microplastics mass afterwards.

2. Terms, definitions and normative references

(1) “**plastic**

material which contains as an essential ingredient a high polymer (3.1) and which, at some stage in its processing into finished products, can be shaped by flow

Note 1 to entry: Plastics consists mainly polymers and minor contents of additives (3.7).

Note 2 to entry: Supplementary to the term “plastic”, “plastic product” is also used. According to ISO 472, a plastic product represents “any material or combination of materials, semi-finished or finished product that is within the scope of ISO/TC 61, Plastics”.

Note 3 to entry: Plastics comprise both thermoplastic (3.3) and thermoset (3.4) materials.” [1]

(2) “**polymer**

chemical compound or mixture of compounds consisting of repeating structural units created through polymerization

Note 1 to entry: In practice above 10 000 Dalton.

Note 2 to entry: Polymers comprise both plastics and elastomers. The latter is excluded from the scope of ISO/TC 61.” [1]

(3) “**additive**

chemicals added to polymers (3.1) to improve/change the individual properties of the specific plastic material

Note 1 to entry: Important additives such as fillers/reinforced materials, softeners and flame retardants are referenced according to ISO 1043-2 to ISO 1043-4.” [1]

(4) “*microplastic*”

any solid plastic particle insoluble in water with any dimension between 1 µm and 1 000 µm (=1 mm)

Note 1 to entry: This term relates to plastic materials within the scope of ISO/TC 61. Rubber, fibres, cosmetic means, etc. are not within the scope.

Note 2 to entry: Typically, a microplastic object represents a particle intentionally added to end-user products, such as cosmetic means, coatings, paints, etc. A microplastic object can also result as a fragment of the respective article.

Note 3 to entry: Microplastics may show various shapes.

Note 4 to entry: The defined dimension is related to the longest distance of the particle”. [1]

(5) “*nanoplastic*”

plastic particles smaller than 1 µm

Note 1 to entry: According to OECD nanoparticles are up to 100 nm.” [1]

3. Abbreviated terms

[SOP] - Standard operating procedure

[TED-GC/MS] - Thermal Extraction Desorption – Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry

4. Method principle

This SOP is a general guide through the sample preparation of milk by citric acid. The sample preparation is based on pH-dependent protein precipitation, resulting in improved filtration and matrix reduction. The sample remains as a filter cake. Higher temperatures can lead to reduced filter residue and therefore more effective matrix reduction. This is due to the reduced viscosity of the fats and fatty acids at higher temperatures.

5. Safety procedures and precautions

Standard safety operating procedures including those of the local labs have to be followed at all times. Special care has to be taken to avoid health risks, while working with small microplastics and nanoplastics.

6. Procedure

6.1 Apparatus and equipment

This section is listing and specifying all equipment used in the procedure:

- Plastic free filter (pore/mesh size at minimum 1 μm or larger)
- Filtration system (e.g Sartorius filtration system)
- Vacuum pump
- 250 mL glass bottle with lid
- Metal spatula
- Tweezers
- Drying oven
- Analytical balance
- 50 mL glass pipette

6.2 Chemicals, reference materials and reagents

This section is listing and specifying all materials used in the procedure:

- Milk powder (e.g. HiPP PRE BIO COMBIOTIK for newborns)
- Citric acid (e.g. $\geq 99.5\%$, water free, Carl Roth, CAS:77-92-9)
- Ethanol (absolute, CAS: 64-17-5)
- MilliQ water (filtered via 200 nm)

6.3 Samples

This section lists the nature of the samples and the amount of sample that is being processed.

This SOP is used for milk powder samples only. A sample weight of low grams (e.g. 5 g) of milk powder is used.

6.4 Performing measurements

6.4.1 General aspects

The filtration system has to be placed in a fume hood.

Use cotton lab coat with low content on fibers and avoid wearing clothes with plastic fibers if possible.

Do not lean over the filtration system during mounting/unmounting or during process.

Do not use any equipment containing plastics or other hydrocarbon-based polymers.

6.4.2 Operation of the equipment

1. Heat the ultrasonic bath to a temperature of 50 °C
2. Put 200 mL of MilliQ water in a water bath at 50 °C.
3. Weight the clean filter on an analytical balance for determining its mass.
4. Place the filtration unit including filter under the fume hood.
5. Close the valve at the filtration system and fill the funnel with 100 mL of MilliQ water (not heated). Wait 20 minutes and check the system for leaks.
6. Open the valve at the filtration unit. Switch on the vacuum pump to remove the water.
7. Switch off the vacuum pump.
8. Close the valve at the filtration unit.

6.4.3 Measurement description

1. Weighing 5 g of milk powder in a 250 mL glass bottle and add a volume of 100 mL of MilliQ water (50 °C). Close the lid carefully.
2. Shake by hand for 30 seconds.
3. Place the loaded bottle in an ultrasonic bath for 5 minutes.
4. Take the glass out of the ultrasonic bath. Open the lid and add 1 g of citric acid. Close the lid carefully.
5. Shake by hand for 30 seconds.
6. Place the loaded bottle in an ultrasonic bath for 5 minutes.
7. Take the glass out of the ultrasonic bath.

8. Shake for 10 seconds by hand. Open the lid carefully and transfer the milk suspension from the glass bottle into the funnel of the filtration system. (Be sure that the filter is in place and the valve at the filtration unit is closed.)
9. Open the valve at the filtration unit. Switch on the vacuum pump.
10. Add 50 mL MilliQ water (50 °C) to the glass bottle. Close the lid carefully. Shake the brown glass bottle for 10 seconds. Open the lid carefully. Transfer the water to the funnel. Repeat number 10 for 3 times.
11. Rinse the wall of the funnel carefully with another 50 mL of MilliQ water (50 °C). Use a glass pipette.
12. Add 50 mL absolute Ethanol to the glass bottle. Close the lid carefully. Shake the brown glass bottle for 10 seconds. Open the lid carefully. Transfer the waters to the funnel.
13. Rinse the wall of the funnel with a glass pipette with 50 mL ethanol.
14. Close the valve at the filtration unit.
15. Switch off the vacuum pump.
16. Remove the funnel of the filtration unit carefully. Take out the filter carefully and place the filter in a glass petri dish.
17. Put the glass petri dish including filter in a drying oven at 50 °C for 2 hours.

7. Calculation of results

The sample can be directly gravimetrically measured on a balance before and after the sample preparation to calculate the matrix reduction. The individual mass of the filter must be subtracted from the gravimetrically determined mass after the sample preparation giving the mass of sieve residue.

$$m (\text{milk before sample preparation}) \\ - m (\text{sieve residue after sample preparation}) = m (\text{milk reduction})$$

8. Quality assurance/ quality control

Milk powder must be stored in a closed vessel under dark, dry and cooled conditions to avoid any contaminations and changes of the milk powder.

9. Measurement uncertainty and traceability

10. Reporting of results

The matrix reduction is determined by difference weighing (7. Calculation of results). The matrix reduction of a milk powder sample of ~5 g is on average 99.9930%, whereby the average mass of the filter residue is 353.7 µg (Table 1).

Table 1: Mass of used milk powder (Mass (initial)), milk powder residue after pretreatment with citric acid (Mass (filter residue) and the corresponding matrix reduction.

	Mass (initial) / g	Mass (filter residue) / g	Matrix reduction / %
	5.09	0.000140	99.99725
	5.11	0.000040	99.99922
	5.03	0.000125	99.99752
Average		0.000102	99.99800
Standard deviation / %		0.000044	0.000872

11. Validation status

in house

ILC

Results can be seen in section 10. Reporting of results.

12. Literature references

[1] ISO/TR 21960:2020, Plastics — Environmental aspects — State of knowledge and methodologies

13. Acknowledgements

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Annexes

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Document change history and approval

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